

Homo and copolymerization of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide : Synthesis and characterization

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Abstract : Free radical homopolymerization of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide (N-PAMI) and copolymerization with methyl methacrylate (MMA) were performed at 65 °C with AIBN as initiator in THF. The molecular weights of polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). Resulting polymers were characterized by density measurement, intrinsic viscosity, solubility, FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The thermal behavior of polymers was determined by TGA. Homo polymer has better thermal stability.

Keywords : Copolymerization, gel permeation chromatography, free radical.

Maleimide functional group is particularly versatile in many unsaturated polymeric systems and has been modified to obtain improved heat resistant, coating adhesives, laminates and fibers¹. Aromatic polyimides are one of the most important classes at high performance polymer, due to their thermal and high temperature mechanical properties². *N*-Substituted maleimide ranks among the group of useful monomers because, when their unit was inserted into some polymer chains behave as thermoplastic resins³.

In recent years there has been considerable interest in the free radical polymerization and copolymerization of *N*-substituted maleimides with various vinyl monomers⁴. In order to investigate the possibility of obtaining better polymers from *N*-substituted maleimide, we have tried to prepare some new better polymers. In this paper we report synthesis and characterization of homopolymer of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide (N-PAMI) and copolymer of N-PAMI with MMA using AIBN as a free radical initiator.

Results and discussion

Effect of solvent on polymer yield : Since free radical homo and copolymerization of maleimides is known to be useful on the synthesis of polymaleimides. This method was applied to their preparation from N-PAMI and vinyl monomers to find suitable condition in which to prepare homo and copolymaleimide with relatively high yield.

The effect of initiator and solvent were investigated in details. The effect of reaction solvents and initiator on yield of H-PAMI and C-PAMI was formed in different pairs of solvent initiator is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Percentage yield of homo and copolymaleimide in various solvent initiators system

Solvent	AIBN (%yield)		BPO (%yield)	
	H-PAMI	C-PAMI	H-PAMI	C-PAMI
THF	24.93	37.07	23.10	36.01
DMF	21.01	22.34	22.53	21.30
Ethylacetate	23.23	26.94	23.10	28.20
<i>p</i> -Dioxane	23.80	29.43	25.40	30.40
Acetone	22.10	31.20	23.00	30.10

The percentage yield of the H-PAMI in the AIBN-DMF system was poor compared to AIBN-dioxane and BPO-dioxane. AIBN-acetone system gave better yield of C-PAMI over the AIBN-EA and BPO-EA system. AIBN-THF system of both polymerizations gave better yield than other solvent-initiator system including BPO-THF system. Examining all the aspect, AIBN-THF system was most suitable for the present homo and copolymerization process.

Effect of time on polymer yield : The effect of reaction solvents and time of stirring on yield of H-PAMI and C-PAMI is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Percentage yield of homo and copolyamide using THF solvent in different time

H-PAMI (%yield)				C-PAMI (%yield)			
12 h	24 h	36 h	48 h	12 h	24 h	36 h	48 h
10.10	24.93	27.20	28.40	12.01	37.90	39.07	40.01

Table 2 revealed that N-PAMI gave better yield of homopolymerization in 36 h in THF solvent and copolymerization in 24 h. Results of Table 2 indicate that polymerization of N-PAMI was very difficult process.

Solubility : Table 3 summarizes the relative solubilities of homo and copolymer samples in number of polar and non-polar solvents at 30 °C. The investigated homo and copolymer samples are soluble in acetone, cyclohexanone, THF, DMF, dichloromethane, DMSO, and solvent and insoluble in CCl₄, xylene, hexane, ethanol, methanol and water.

Table 3. Solubility behaviour of monomer, homopolymer and copolymer in polar and non-polar solvents at 30 °C

Solvent	N-PAMI	H-PAMI	C-PAMI
Acetone	S	S	S
Cyclohexanone	S	S	S
p-Dioxane	IS	S	S
THF	S	S	S
DMF	S	S	S
Dichloromethane	S	S	S
DMSO	S	S	S
Chloroform	S	S	S
CCl ₄	IS	IS	S
Xylene	IS	IS	IS
Toluene	IS	IS	PS
Hexane	PS	IS	IS
Methanol	IS	IS	IS
Ethanol	IS	IS	IS
Water	IS	IS	IS

S - Soluble, PS - Partially soluble, IS - Insoluble.

Physical properties : The density, intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ and molecular weight of the present polymer samples are listed in Table 4. The value of intrinsic viscosity in DMF at 30 °C, molecular weight and density are in decreasing order of C-PAMI > H-PAMI. The value of $[\eta]$ depends on molecular weight as well as on the size of polymer coil in given solution. Table 4 reveals that, as the content of N-PAMI are increases, the value of $[\eta]$ decreases as well as molecular weight are decreases. The value of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ depends on molecular weight

Table 4. The intrinsic viscosity, density and molecular weight of H-PAMI and C-PAMI

Polymer	Density ρ (g/cm ³)	η dl/g	M_w (g/mol)
H-PAMI	0.8102	0.210	5675.9
C-PAMI	0.8491	0.240	25581.4

as well as structure of polymer. Although it increases with molecular weight but not linearly. Intrinsic viscosity of copolymer is greater than homopolymer since molecular weight of copolymer is more than that of homopolymer.

According to Mark-Houwink equation, intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ and molecular weight is given by

$$\eta = KM^\alpha$$

$$\log \eta = \log K + \alpha \log M$$

Here α is characteristic constant depend on structure of polymer.

Although the study is not completed but from the data so far obtained by the authors of this paper, it can be inferred that in case of homopolymers (Table 5, Fig. 1), the curve between $\log M_w$ and $\log [\eta] \times 10^3$ is not a

Table 5. The intrinsic viscosity, molecular weight and their log value of homopolymers (temperature 30 °C)

Polymer	M_w (g/mol)	$\log M_w$	$[\eta] \times 10^3$ dl/g	$\log [\eta] \times 10^3$
HPAMI	5675	3.7539	210	2.3222
HDNPAMI	8840	3.9464	215	2.3324
HPNPAMI	9946	3.9976	235	2.3710
HMNPAMI	8848	3.9468	220	2.3424
HONPAMI	5365	3.7295	202	2.3053

HPAMI = Poly-N-(phenylamino)maleimide, HDNPAMI = Poly-N-[(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino]maleimide, HPNPAMI = Poly-N-[(4-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide, HMNPAMI = Poly-N-[(3-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide, HONPAMI = Poly-N-[(2-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide.

Fig. 1. Plot between $\log \eta \times 10^3$ and $\log M_w$ of homopolymers.

good straight line ($R^2 = 0.7695$ for five point), while in case of copolymers (Table 6, Fig. 2) the law is applied very well i.e. linear relation between $\log M_w$ and $\log [\eta] \times 10^3$ ($R^2 = 0.7695$ for five point).

Table 6. The intrinsic viscosity, molecular weight and their log value of copolymers (temperature 30 °C)

Polymer	M_w (g/mol)	$\log M_w$	$[\eta] \times 10^3$ dl/g	$\log [\eta] \times 10^3$
CPAMI	25581.6	4.4079	240	2.3802
CDNPAMI	28970.1	4.4619	280	2.4471
CPNPAMI	39663.2	4.5984	385	2.5854
CMNPAMI	32063.2	4.5060	310	2.4913
CONPAMI	29013.2	4.4626	290	2.4623

CPAMI = Copoly-*N*-(phenylamino)maleimide-co-MMA, CDNPAMI = Copoly-*N*-[(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino]maleimide-co-MMA, CPNPAMI = Copoly-*N*-[(4-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide-co-MMA, CMNPAMI = Copoly-*N*-[(3-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide-co-MMA, CONPAMI = Copoly-*N*-[(2-nitrophenyl)amino]maleimide-co-MMA.

Fig. 2. Plot between $\log \eta \times 10^3$ and $\log M_w$ of copolymers.

Spectral characterization : The FT-IR spectrum and ^1H NMR spectrum (300 MHz in CDCl_3) of H-PAMI are shown following peak and chemical shift. The absence of a sharp band at 911 cm^{-1} and chemical shift δ at 6.8 ppm due to $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ in a monomer having a vinyl group, such as monomer N-PAMI indicate the formation of polymer via vinyl group polymerization.

The δ observed at 6.81 ppm due to $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ in the monomer has shifted to 4.5–4.9 ppm in the polymer as a result of the formation of semi flexible poly substituted methine $-(\text{CH}-\text{CH})_n-$ group⁵. The δ for methine $-(\text{CH}-\text{CH})_n-$ protons has been reported in the range from 3.0 to 5.0 ppm depending upon the substitution in maleimide. The value of δ in the range 3.0–4.0 for poly [*N*-[4-*N'*-(α -methylbenzyl)amino]carbonylphenyl]maleimide have been reported⁶. The broad peak at 7.59–7.18 ppm corresponds to 5 Ar-H and N-H singlet at 3.745. The presence of absorption bands at 1778.4 and 1716.7 cm^{-1} due to sym-

metric and asymmetric stretching of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ in the five member imide ring indicates that the imide ring remained intact in the polymerization. The imide group is also confirmed from the bands observed at 1495.8 (Ar-N stretch), 1416.2 (C-N stretch), 1164 (C-N-C), 1170 and 760 cm^{-1} . The broad medium intense band at 1596.8, strong intense band at 1571.0 and a medium band at 1495.8 correspond to the aromatic (C=C) band. The broad stretching bands at 3433.6 represent secondary amine (-NH).

^1H NMR spectra of the copolymer showed the following chemical shifts. The δ at 7.27–6.91 ppm is 5H of aromatic phenyl ring. A δ at 4.5–5.0 ppm appeared for 2H of $-(\text{CH}-\text{CH})-$ in the polymer main chain and δ observed at 3.4–4.6 ppm corresponds to overlapping of 1H in -N-H group of amino phenyl maleimide segment and 3H ($-\text{OCH}_3$) of MMA segment. The δ in the range 0.8–1.4 ppm is of 2H of methyl group while at 1.43–2.20 ppm for 2H of methylene group. ^1H NMR spectrum also confirmed the consumption of all the vinyl groups of the comonomers because absorptions of vinyl groups of both monomers are absent in the spectrum, for example, 7.1 ppm for vinyl protons of N-PAMI and 5.0–6.0 ppm for MMA. This indicated that the polymerization happened via the opening of the double bond.

The major characteristic absorption bands are observed at 3319 cm^{-1} (-NH stretch), 1780.3 and 1724.2 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ symmetric and asymmetric stretch in a five member imide ring and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch of ester), 1602.7 and 1496.9 (aromatic, C=C and amide group). These characteristic bands confirm that units of both the monomers N-PAMI and MMA are present in the copolymer samples.

Thermal properties : It is well known that polymaleimide is potential heat and chemical resistant material so maleimide is widely used as a monomer for modified polymeric systems. Only single step degradation at temperature of over 300 °C was observed for polymaleimide in TGA. The thermograms were obtained by heating homopolymer and copolymer sample in air at 10 °C/min. The typical TGA curves are obtained of H-PAMI and C-PAMI. The results of percentage weight loss suffered from 100 °C to 600 °C at 100 intervals are furnished in Table 8.

The initial decomposition temperature T_i , temperature for maximum weight loss T_{max} and final decomposition temperature T_f of first degradation step are given in Table 7. The results in Table 6 indicate that the relative thermal stability on the basis of T_i follows on the order H-PAMI > C-PAMI.

As the content of N-PAMI in the feed is 100% in the

Table 7. Thermal behaviour of homopolymer and copolymer

Polymer	T_i	T_{max}	T_f	Residue at 500 °C
H-PAMI	290 °C	320 °C	350 °C	29%
	350 °C	550 °C	720 °C	
C-PAMI	220 °C	300 °C	330 °C	10%
	330 °C	400 °C	550 °C	

Table 8. Percentage weight loss of homo and copolymer at various temperatures from the TGA

Polymer	200 °C	300 °C	400 °C	500 °C	600 °C
	Weight loss (%)				
H-PAMI	1%	50%	67%	71%	75%
C-PAMI	2%	49%	84%	89%	90%

homopolymer began to decompose at higher T_i and weight loss for the first step became smaller. The first step weight loss ranged from 50–62%. The total weight loss of H-PAMI upto 600 °C is 71%. The copolymer C-PAMI was decomposed through a one step procedure. As the copolymer sample content of N-PAMI is 50% the copolymer began to decompose at lower T_i and weight loss for the first step became larger as compared to homopolymer. The first step weight loss was range to 60 to 75%. The weight loss of C-PAMI upto 600 °C is 89–90%. Table 7 reveals that weight loss was below 0.8 to 8% up to 300 °C in copolymer sample and 100% content of N-PAMI feed in homopolymer weight loss was below 0.1 to 2% upto 300 °C. The results in Table 7 indicate that the thermal stability tends to increase from the copolymer to homopolymer.

Experimental

Materials : Phenyl hydrazine was distilled and maleic anhydride was recrystallized from acetone before use. Methyl methacrylate (MMA) (CDH) was shaken two to three times with 5% NaOH to eliminate hydroquinone inhibitor, dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 for 8 h and distilled. The head and tail fractions were discarded. AIBN (2,2'-azobis-isobutyronitrile) (spectrochem.) was recrystallized twice from methanol prior to use. BPO (benzoyl peroxide) (CDH) were used as received. THF was purified by distillation after being refluxed for 2 h in the presence of sodium. DMF and methanol used in the present work were of analytical grade and were used as received.

Measurements : ^1H NMR spectra of monomer and polymer samples were taken in CDCl_3 on a Bruker DPX-200/DPX-300 spectrometer at 200/300 MHz. The internal reference used was TMS. FT-IR spectra of the mono-

mer and polymer samples were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–400 cm^{-1}) FT-IR spectrometer, using KBr pellet technique. The viscosities measurements were carried out in DMF at 30 ± 0.2 °C, using Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Elemental analysis was made on Carlo-Erba Model NA 500 series analyzer. The thermograms in air were obtained on a Mettler TA-3000 system, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Methods :

Preparation of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide (N-PAMI) monomer : *N*-(Phenylamino)maleimide was synthesized by condensation of maleic anhydride with phenyl hydrazine followed by cyclodehydration using P_2O_5 and H_2SO_4 .⁷

Phenyl hydrazine (0.1 *M*) solution in DMF was gradually added dropwise with stirring into maleic anhydride (0.1) solution in DMF for a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. This solution was poured in crushed ice water. The light yellow mass of *N*-(phenylamino)maleamic acid (N-PAMA) was filtered and dried at 55 °C. It was recrystallized from methanol to obtained pure N-PAMA.

20.6 g (0.1 *M*) N-PAMA in 30 ml DMF solution was taken, then the solution of 7.4 g P_2O_5 and 1.0 ml H_2SO_4 in 35 ml DMF was added dropwise over a period of 20 min with constant stirring. After stirring for 2 h at 70 °C, the reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice water. The yellow precipitate of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide (N-PAMI) was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dried. N-PAMI was recrystallized from methanol. Overall yield was 72% and m.p. was obtained 215 °C. The IR spectrum showed absorption frequencies 3062.2 (aromatic and alkene C-H stretch), 1778.4 and 1716.7 (symmetric and asymmetric stretch of C=O in a five member imide ring), 1596.8, 1517.0, 1495.8 (C=C aromatic), 1416.2 (C-N stretch) cm^{-1} .

^1H NMR (300 MHz, TMS, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 7.5–6.8 (4H, 2d, phenyl), 3.74 (1H, s, N-H), 6.3 and 7.1 (2H, s, O=C-CH=CH-C=O).

Polymerization :

Homopolymerization : Radical homopolymerization of *N*-(phenylamino)maleimide was carried out in THF solvent using AIBN as a free radical initiator at 65 °C.

N-PAMI (1.88 g, 0.01 mol) and THF (70 ml) were placed in round bottom flask with reflux condenser. To this solution AIBN 20 mg was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed at 65 °C for 24 h. No polymer or very less polymer was formed if the reaction was carried

out upto 24 h. Yield was about 24.93% for 36 h. The homopolymer H-PAMI was isolated in excess quantity of methanol-water mixture. Pure polymer H-PAMI was obtained by first dissolving it in THF and then reprecipitating by methanol-water mixture. It was dried at 60 °C under vacuum. A summary of polymerization conditions and physical characteristics of H-PAMI are presented in Table 7. Various homopolymer samples were obtained using different solvent-initiator combination. The percentage yield of homopolymer samples using different solvent and initiator are presented in Table 1.

Copolymerization : Calculated amount of monomer N-PAMI with MMA in 70 ml THF solvent were taken in a round bottom flask. Then 20 mg AIBN was added to the reaction mixture as a free radical initiator. The copolymerization reaction was carried out at 65 °C for 24 h. Polymer samples were isolated in water containing 20% methanol. The copolymer was purified by first dissolving in THF and then, reprecipitating in excess quantity of methanol-water mixture. The precipitated copolymer was washed several times and dried at 60 °C under vacuum.

A summary of polymerization conditions and physical characteristics of C-PAMI are presented in Table 9. Various copolymer samples were obtained using different sol-

Table 9. Radical polymerization and copolymerization of N-PAMI and MMA in THF at 65 °C

Polymer code	Feed mole fraction of PAMI	Polymerization time (h)	Yield (%)	N (%)	Appearance
H-PAMI	1.0	36	24.93	15.4	Light yellow
C-PAMI	0.5	24	37.07	4.57	Light yellow

vent-initiator combination. The percentage yield of copolymer samples using different solvent and initiator are presented in Table 1.

Conclusions : Synthesis, through free radical polymerization, homopolymerization of N-PAMI and copolymerization of N-PAMI with MMA has been investigated. These synthesized polymers are having good performance viz. high thermal stability, high solubility in organic solvents, high intrinsic viscosity, comparatively lesser density than water and higher molecular weight. Homopolymer show good thermal stability than copolymer and it degrade in two-step. In case of copolymers linear relationship between $\log [\eta]$ and $\log M_w$ has been formed.

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